

Inference Attacks Against Genomic Data-Sharing Beacons

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Abstract. Genomic datasets are often associated with sensitive phenotypes. Therefore, the leak of membership information is a major privacy risk. Genomic beacons aim to provide a secure, and standardized interface for data sharing. Recent studies have demonstrated that it is possible to determine whether the victim is in the dataset, by repeatedly querying the beacon for his/her single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). In this work, we propose a novel re-identification attack and show that the privacy risk is more serious than previously thought. Our method is based on the fact that alleles at different loci are not necessarily independent. We use the linkage disequilibrium and a high-order Markov chain-based algorithm for the inference. We show that in a beacon with 65 individuals from the CEU population, we can infer membership of individuals with 95% confidence with only 5 queries, even when SNPs with minor allele frequencies (MAF) less than 0.05 are hidden as a countermeasure (as proposed in previous work). This means, we need less than 0.5% of the number of queries that existing works require to determine beacon membership under the same conditions. We further show that, countermeasures such as hiding certain parts of the genome or setting a query budget for the user would fail to protect the privacy of the participants under our adversary model.

1 Introduction

Genomic data-sharing beacons are the gateways that let users and data owners exchange information without -in theory- disclosing any personal information. More specifically, the user submits a query, asking whether a genome exists in the beacon with a certain nucleotide at a certain position, and the beacon answers “yes” or “no”. The Beacon Project is an initiative by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) which creates

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policies to ensure standardized and secure sharing of genomic data. However, Shringarpure and Bustamante recently introduced a likelihood-ratio test (LRT) that predicts if an individual is in the beacon or not, given the VCF file of the target (dubbed as the SB attack) [5]. Very recently, Raisaro *et al.* showed that if the attacker has access to the MAFs of the population, s/he can sort the victim’s SNPs and query the SNPs starting from the one with the lowest MAF (dubbed as the Optimal attack) [3]. This is different than to the SB attack which queries for random SNPs. As low MAF SNPs are more informative, Raisaro *et al.* show that fewer queries are needed to re-identify an individual. We demonstrate that beacons are more vulnerable than previously thought and that the proposed countermeasures in the literature still fail to protect the privacy of the individuals. The contributions of this paper can be listed as follows:

- By inferring query results and alleles at certain positions, we show that it is possible to significantly decrease the number of required queries compared to other attacks in the literature [5, 3].
- We show that beacons are vulnerable even under a weaker adversary model, in which important parts of a victim’s genome are concealed (such as all SNPs with an MAF less than a threshold).
- We discuss the feasibility and the effectiveness of the proposed countermeasures in the literature and show that using the presented attack models, the participants are still under risk.

2 Material and Methods

In the following, we will first describe recent attacker models (i.e. SB attack and the Optimal attack [5, 3]), followed by our proposed attacks. In our first proposed attack, the attacker not only has access to MAFs of the victim’s population, but also knows the corresponding linkage disequilibrium values (QI-attack). In the second model, the attacker has the same background knowledge as the QI-attack but also has access to anonymized VCF files of people from the victim’s population from public sources such as HapMap [1] or 1000 Genomes Project [6] (GI-attack). In this model, the attacker also infers the possibly hidden SNPs. We consider two scenarios; Scenario 1 assumes the attacker has access to the full genome of the victim. Scenario 2 considers a more realistic attacker model, in which SNPs are systematically hidden. In other words, SNPs with an $MAF < t$ are not available to the attacker. Note that, Scenario 1 is not applicable to the GI-attack.

The LRT proposed by Shringarpure and Bustamante is based on the “yes” responses of the queried beacon using a target’s VCF file [5]. The queried SNPs are picked randomly from the victim’s heterozygous SNP positions. The null hypothesis (H_0) refers to the query genome being not in the beacon database. Under the alternative hypothesis (H_1) the query genome is a member of the beacon. The attacker model is visualized in Figure 1(a). The log-likelihood under the null hypothesis has been defined as

$$L_{H_0}(R) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \log(1 - D_N) + (1 - x_i) \log(D_N), \quad (1)$$

where R is the response set and D_N the probability that no individual in the beacon has the queried allele at that position. x_i is the answer of the beacon to the query at position i (1 for yes, 0 for no), and n is the total number of queries. Accordingly, the log-likelihood of the alternative hypothesis has been stated as

$$L_{H_1}(R) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \log(1 - \delta D_{N-1}) + (1 - x_i) \log(\delta D_{N-1}), \quad (2)$$

where D_{N-1} represents the probability of no individual except for the queried person having the queried SNP. δ represents a possible sequencing error. Finally, the LRT statistic of Shringarpure and Bustamante is stated as: $A = nB + C \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$, where B and C are defined as $B = \log(D_N/\delta D_{N-1})$ and $C = \log(\delta D_{N-1}(1 - D_N/D_N(1 - \delta D_{N-1})))$, respectively. The null hypothesis is rejected for any A that is less than a certain threshold.

The Optimal attack introduced by Raisaro *et al.* also integrates publicly available MAF information into the attackers background knowledge [3]. In this attack, the victim’s SNPs are sorted with respect to their MAF. The beacon is queried accordingly, starting from the first heterozygous SNP with the lowest MAF. The model of this attack is illustrated in Figure 1(b). In this setting, the computations of D_{N-1} and D_N depend on the queried position i and change at each query, such that $D_{N-1}^i = (1 - f_i)^{2N-2}$ and $D_N^i = (1 - f_i)^{2N}$, where f_i represents the minor allele frequency of the SNP at position i (the value of A also changes accordingly).

Fig. 1. System models of the four attacker models (a) SB attack [5], (b) Optimal attack [3], (c) QI-attack and (d) GI-attack. Upper-case letters represent the major allele at a SNP position and the lower-case letters the corresponding minor allele. The SB attack randomly selects the minor allele from heterozygous SNP positions of the victim and queries those. The Optimal attack first sorts the heterozygous SNPs regarding their MAF and queries for the minor alleles starting with the lowest frequency. Depending on the threshold t , SNPs with an $MAF < t$ are hidden and not available to the attacker. The QI-attack is identical to the Optimal attack but extends it by inferring beacon answers using LD correlations between SNP pairs. The GI-attack infers the hidden SNPs with $MAFs < t$ by using a high-order Markov chain and queries the beacon for the minor alleles of those positions.

2.1 Query Inference Attack (QI-attack)

The QI-attack uses pairwise SNP correlations (linkage disequilibrium - LD) in order to infer the answers of unposed queries from previously answered queries. The attacker calculates the probability of the two minor alleles occurring together. Let p_2 be the minor allele frequency of SNP A (with minor allele a) and q_2 the minor allele frequency of SNP B (with minor allele b). If A and B are in an LD relationship, the LD value between them increases the probability of two major or two minor alleles in these loci occurring together. This can be calculated as follows; $Pr(ab) = p_2q_2 + D$, where D resembles the strength of the correlation of the two SNPs. On this basis, the attacker constructs a SNP network that uses weighted, directed edges between SNPs in high LD. The weight corresponds to the calculated probabilities. Figure 1(c) shows the model of this attack. First, the attacker selects the SNPs to be queried. This step is identical to the Optimal attack and leads to a set of candidate SNPs S to be queried, starting from the lowest MAF SNP_i . As a second step, if any non-queried SNP_j in S is a neighbor of SNP_i in the SNP network, the attacker infers the result of the query and does not send a query for SNP_j . In the following, we show the null and the alternative hypotheses including the inference error:

$$L_{H_0}(R) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(x_i \log(1 - D_N^i) + (1 - x_i) \log(D_N^i) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma x_i \log(1 - D_N^j) + \gamma(1 - x_i) \log(D_N^j) \right) \quad (3)$$

$$L_{H_1}(R) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(x_i \log(1 - \delta D_{N-1}^i) + (1 - x_i) \log(\delta D_{N-1}^i) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma x_i \log(1 - \delta D_{N-1}^j) + \gamma(1 - x_i) \log(\delta D_{N-1}^j) \right) \quad (4)$$

Here, n is the number of posed queries, m is the number of neighbors that can be inferred for each posed query x_i and γ corresponds to the confidence of the inferred answer, obtained from the SNP network. Accordingly, Λ is calculated as follows: $\Lambda = L_{H_0}(R) - L_{H_1}(R)$.

By eliminating unnecessary queries, this attacker model requires less queries to the server than the Optimal attack while achieving the same response set.

2.2 Genome Inference Attack (GI-attack)

The GI-attack extends the QI-attack, in order to cope with possible countermeasures on the victim’s side. Individuals may publicly share their genomes by taking necessary precautions, such as hiding their sensitive SNP positions with MAFs $< t$. This attack infers the victim’s hidden SNPs. The attacker uses a high-order Markov chain to model SNP correlations as described by Samani *et al.* [4].

The process of the attack is shown in Figure 1(d). Depending on the threshold t , the attacker infers SNP positions with an MAF $< t$ that are hidden in the victim’s VCF file. Based on the victim’s genome sequence, the attacker calculates the likelihood of the victim having a heterozygous position at the chosen SNP position i as follows

$$P_k(SNP_i) = P(SNP_i | SNP_{i-1}, SNP_{i-2}, \dots, SNP_{i-k}), \quad (5)$$

where k is the order of the Markov chain. In order to use a high-order Markov chain to infer hidden SNPs, genome sequences from public sources such as the 1000 Genomes project or HapMap can be used to train the model. Samani *et al.* define the k^{th} -order model as follows:

$$P_k(SNP_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } F(SNP_{i-k,i-1}) = 0 \\ \frac{F(SNP_{i-k,i})}{F(SNP_{i-k,i-1})} & \text{if } F(SNP_{i-k,i-1}) > 0, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $F(SNP_{i,j})$ is the frequency of occurrence of the sequence that contains SNP_i to SNP_j . If the calculated likelihood of the victim having a heterozygous position is high enough (in this case equal to 1), the attacker queries the beacon for the inferred SNP position, starting from the SNP with the lowest MAF.

3 Results

We evaluated the performance of the four attacks with 105 people from the CEU population of the HapMap dataset, where 65 people were in the beacon and 40 people were not. In order to test the beacon for both hypotheses, we used the 40 individuals that are not in the beacon and 20 additional from the beacon. The LD values, allele frequencies, and genotype data were also obtained from the CEU dataset of the HapMap project [1].

We show the power curves for each attack at 5% false positive rate in Figure 2 and number of queries needed for re-identification at 5% false

Fig. 2. (a) Close-up of the power curves, where number of queries < 10 . (b) Power curves of the Optimal attack [3], the QI-attack, and the GI-attack for different thresholds of t on a beacon with 65 members constructed with individuals from the CEU dataset of the HapMap project. t indicates the threshold up to which SNPs with an $\text{MAF} < t$ are hidden as a countermeasure.

positive rate in Table 1. We empirically determine the distribution of Λ under the null hypothesis using the 40 people who are not in the beacon. When Λ is less than a threshold, the null hypothesis is rejected. Similar to Raisaro *et al.* [3], we reject the null hypothesis when $\Lambda < t_\alpha$. We find the threshold t_α from the null hypothesis with $\alpha = 0.05$. The power $1 - \beta$ is then the proportion of $\Lambda < t_\alpha$ for all individuals in the control set.

We observed that the SB attack, the Optimal attack and the QI-attack require more queries to reach the desired confidence level when the threshold t increases. The SB attack requires the highest number of queries, between 1,400 and 56,800. The QI-attack requires 30% less number of queries on average than the Optimal attack. The GI-attack requires 5 queries for all tested thresholds of t . For the GI-attack, we used a 4th-order Markov chain.

Compared to the step-wise increased behavior of the power curves for the Optimal attack, the power curve for the QI-attack shows a zig-zag behavior. As “no” responses of the beacon are important to build a sufficient null hypothesis, an individual for which only “yes” responses were

received shows the same Λ behavior as an individual with the alternative hypothesis. The reason for the zig-zag behavior of the power is the difference in the amount of inferred queries per posed query for those individuals without a “no” response. Since Λ decreases significantly for a high amount of inferred queries and t_α is determined empirically, t_α can also decrease again which causes the power drop. Nevertheless, when the null hypothesis is successfully built and all necessary case individuals received a sufficient amount of “no” responses, the value of t_α stabilizes and the power reaches 100%.

As t increases only more common SNPs are available to the attacker which means that the likelihood of another individual in the beacon having the same allele increases. When the beacon was queried for each of the 40 people who are not in the beacon, the SB attack was not able to receive a “no” response with 100,000 queries (i) for 4 people when SNPs with an MAF < 0.04 were hidden and (ii) for 12 people when SNPs with an MAF < 0.05 were hidden. Therefore, it was not possible to build a sufficient null hypothesis. The Optimal and the QI-attack require a significantly higher amount of queries to build the null hypothesis for larger t values. The GI-attack successfully built a null hypothesis and determined the correct status for all 40 individuals despite the high threshold of t with only a few queries.

Table 1. Average number of queries needed to receive the first negative response for the SB attack [5], the Optimal attack [3], the QI-attack, and the GI-attack for different thresholds of t on a beacon with 65 members constructed with individuals from the CEU dataset of the HapMap project. t indicates the threshold up to which SNPs with an MAF $< t$ are hidden. As the GI-attack concentrates on inferring hidden parts of the genome, we do not consider $t = 0$ (nothing is hidden) for the GI-attack.

t	# of queries			
	SB attack	Optimal attack	QI-attack	GI-attack
0	1,418	7	5	NA
0.03	19,525	415	282	5
0.05	56,758	1,776	1,247	5

4 Discussion

By developing a statistical test in 2008, Homer *et al.* showed how the DNA of an individual can be identified within a complex genomic mixture, even

if only 0.1 % of the DNA in the mixture belongs to that individual [2]. Recent works by Shringarpure and Bustamante [5] and Raisaro *et al.* [3] have shown that beacon servers do not protect their members' privacy as successful as previously thought. As beacons are often associated with a certain phenotype, the membership identification of an individual could leak sensitive phenotype information. Therefore, they proposed countermeasures to better protect the beacon members privacy. In this work we have shown that beacon membership can be detected with a low number of queries and high confidence, even if beacon administrators and their members apply countermeasures to ensure a higher security level. Overcoming the proposed countermeasures is possible by including publicly available information such as MAF, LD, and VCF files (from e.g., HapMap [1] or 1000 Genomes Project [6]) into the attacker model.

Shringarpure and Bustamante discussed different countermeasures, such as increasing the beacon size, sharing only small genomic regions, using single population beacons, not publishing the metadata of a beacon, or adding control samples to the beacon dataset [5].

Raisaro *et al.* have analyzed the behavior of the beacon when applying three different countermeasures [3]. Firstly, they propose the beacon should only respond "yes" for an allele if it exists in more than one individual in the beacon. The second countermeasure adds noise to the responses of the beacon and therefore answers "no" instead of "yes" to some queries. However, this countermeasure significantly reduces the utility of the data and is unacceptable for researchers working on data-sharing beacons. Lastly, Raisaro *et al.* proposed a query budget as a countermeasure. That is, every member of the beacon is assigned with a certain budget that is reduced if a query to the beacon matches one of their SNP positions. If the budget of a beacon member is depleted, the beacon stops including the member into the beacon responses. An attacker using the QI-attack can use SNP correlations to overcome this budget countermeasure. Assuming the attacker is trying to identify beacon membership of the victim, by using the Optimal attack, a beacon applying the budget countermeasure would start returning false responses, which would lead to a wrong conclusion by the attacker. An attacker using the QI-attack would not exhaust the budget but still be able to determine the victim's beacon membership.

Finally, the GI-attack shows that even if genomes do not contain any SNPs with low MAFs, the individual's privacy is not ensured, as it is possible to infer these positions using publicly available datasets (e.g. HapMap [1] or 1000 Genomes Project [6]). Is the population of the victim

unknown to the attacker, the attacker can use clustering of genomes in order to determine which population the victim's genome is the closest to.

5 Conclusion

Throughout the course of this work, we showed that data-sharing beacons are sensitive to re-identification attacks. Additionally, we showed that countermeasures that do not consider the MAFs and correlations of SNPs fail to protect the beacon members' privacy. Furthermore, even if individuals apply countermeasures before releasing their genome, such as systematically hiding SNPs with low MAFs, their privacy could still be at stake. As future work, we are working on new mitigation strategies to protect beacon members' privacy.

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